

INDIVIDUAL GENE GENEALOGY RESULTS

Supplemental Fig. S1. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of *Opheodrys aestivus* based on mitochondrial cytochrome b (cytb) data. Symbols on nodes indicate branch support values: green indicates Bayesian posterior probability (BPP) > 0.95 and Maximum likelihood bootstrap (MLBS) > 75, yellow indicates BPP > 0.95 and MLBS < 75. Symbols at branch tips correspond to the sampling localities in Fig. 1: yellow: peninsular Florida clade, red: central Texas clade, blue: main clade.

Supplemental Fig. S2. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of *Opheodrys aestivus* based on concatenated analysis of nuclear loci from Sanger sequence data, partitioned by locus. Symbols on nodes correspond to branch support values: green indicates Bayesian posterior probability (BPP) > 0.95 and Maximum likelihood bootstrap (MLBS) > 75, yellow indicates BPP > 0.95 and MLBS < 75. Symbols at branch tips correspond to the sampling localities in Fig. 1: yellow: peninsular Florida clade, red: central Texas clade, blue: main clade.

Supplemental Fig. S3. Maximum likelihood gene genealogy based on phased LAT sequence data. Symbols on nodes correspond to branch support values: green indicates Bayesian posterior probability (BPP) > 0.95 and Maximum likelihood bootstrap (MLBS) > 75, yellow indicates BPP > 0.95 and MLBS < 75. Symbols at branch tips correspond to the sampling localities in Fig. 1: yellow: peninsular Florida clade, red: central Texas clade, blue: main clade. Within the Main + Texas clade, samples included in the Texas clade are indicated with red squares next to sample

labels.

Supplemental Fig. S4. Maximum likelihood gene genealogy based on phased NT3 sequence data. Symbols on nodes correspond to branch support values: green indicates Bayesian posterior probability (BPP) > 0.95 and Maximum likelihood bootstrap (MLBS) > 75, yellow indicates BPP > 0.95 and MLBS < 75. Samples recovered from Florida or Texas clades in full concatenated phylogenetic analyses indicated with yellow or red squares, respectively, at tip labels. Samples not labeled otherwise were recovered in the *O. aestivus* main clade.

Supplemental Fig. S5. Maximum likelihood gene genealogy based on phased PRLR sequence data. Symbols on nodes correspond to branch support values: green indicates Bayesian posterior probability (BPP) > 0.95 and Maximum likelihood bootstrap (MLBS) > 75, yellow indicates BPP > 0.95 and MLBS < 75. Samples recovered from Florida or Texas clades in full concatenated phylogenetic analyses indicated with yellow or red squares, respectively, at tip labels. Samples not labeled otherwise were recovered in the *O. aestivus* main clade.

STRUCTURE RESULTS

Supplemental Fig. S6. A. Mean $\ln P(D) \pm S.E.$ and B. ΔK for all values of K tested from Structure analyses including all samples of *Opheodrys*, as calculated in Structure Harvester.

Supplemental Fig. S7. Population inferences based on Structure analyses including all samples of *Opheodrys* for $K = 1 - 8$ populations as summarized by Clumpak. Samples grouped by major clade inferred from concatenated phylogenetic analyses and sorted from northeast to southwest within each clade. Numeric sample labels correspond to those listed in Appendix 1.

Supplemental Fig. S8. A. Mean $\ln P(D) \pm S.E.$ and B. ΔK for all values of K tested from Structure analyses including all samples of *Opheodrys*, but with the main clade of *O. aestivus* subsampled to minimize differences in sample size among phylogenetic lineages, as calculated in Structure Harvester.

Supplemental Fig. S9. Population inferences based on Structure analyses of all *Opheodrys* samples, but with the main clade of *O. aestivus* randomly subsampled to minimize differences in sample size, for $K = 1 - 8$ clusters as summarized by Clumpak. Samples grouped by major clade inferred from concatenated phylogenetic analyses and sorted from northeast to southwest within each clade. Numeric sample labels correspond to those listed in Appendix 1.

Supplemental Fig. S10. A. Mean $\ln P(D) \pm S.E.$ and B. ΔK for all values of K tested based on Structure analyses including samples in the main clade of *Opheodrys aestivus* (blue cluster in $K=2$ plot of Supplemental Fig. S2), as calculated in Structure Harvester.

Supplemental Fig. S11. Population inferences from Structure analyses of samples included in the main clade of *Opheodrys aestivus* (blue cluster in $K=2$ plot in Supplemental Fig. S2) for $K = 1 - 6$ populations as summarized by Clumpak. Numeric sample labels correspond to those listed in Appendix 1.

Supplemental Fig. S12. A. Mean $\ln P(D) \pm S.E.$ and B. ΔK for all values of K tested from Structure analyses including samples of *Opheodrys* from the second cluster from the full analyses (orange cluster in $K=2$ plot in Supplemental Fig. S2; includes all samples except those in the main clade of *O. aestivus*), as calculated in Structure Harvester.

Supplemental Fig. S13. Population inferences based on Structure analyses including all *Opheodrys* samples from the second cluster in full analyses (orange cluster in $K=2$ plot in Supplemental Figure S2; includes all samples not included in *O. aestivus* main clade) for $K = 1 - 6$ populations as summarized by Clumpak. Samples grouped by major clade inferred in concatenated phylogenetic analyses and sorted from northeast to southwest within each clade. Numeric sample labels correspond to those listed in Appendix 1.